

EXPLORING RESEARCH THEMES IN THE ISLAMIC CAPITAL MARKET

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the development of research around Islamic Capital Market. The research was conducted from 2004 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Islamic Capital Market". Based on the search results, there were 239 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Islamic Capital Market is divided into 13 clusters and 321 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 6 main themes related to Islamic Capital Market.

Keywords: *Islamic Capital Market, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review*

I. INTRODUCTION

The capital market is an organized and structured financial system where capital is traded over the long term, both equity and debt, between investors and issuers, with the aim of developing investment. In 1912, the capital market in Indonesia began to be managed and operated by the Dutch colonial government in Batavia. However, in 1942, the capital market stopped operating due to the World War which caused the Netherlands to be pressured by Germany (Sepdiana, 2019).

In previous research, the Islamic capital market in Indonesia has experienced significant development in recent years. Islamic Capital Markets are capital markets that operate in accordance with Islamic sharia principles, which prohibit the practices of *riba* (interest), speculation, and investment in sectors that are considered haram in Islam, such as gambling, alcohol, and pornography (Apriani, 2022). Meanwhile, the number of companies registered on the Islamic capital market continues to increase from year to year. At the end of 2021, there were 102 companies listed on the Indonesian sharia stock exchange (BEI). Apart from that, the number of investors in the Islamic capital market also continues to increase from year to year (Sholeh, 2020).

The development of the Islamic Capital Market has gone through various processes and has high prospects, which ultimately resulted in several Islamic Capital Market instruments. In 2020, the Islamic Capital Market can be said to be good, because the number of investors increased by 3.31 million or grew by 26.27%. In 2021, the number of Islamic Capital Market investors reached 7.84 million, while in 2022 the number of investors shot up to 9.54 million or grew by 27.38% (Ramadhan, 2021). In the current era of digitalization, one of the Islamic Capital Market securities instruments that is gaining popularity is sukuk. Sukuk products are an alternative in choosing investments, where the return rate on sukuk has higher returns than deposits (Jannah, 2021). However, there are still people who do not know and understand sukuk products due to a lack of education about sukuk, both real and virtual, so that some people have little interest in investing in sukuk products. Therefore, the author will discuss the influence of digitalization in influencing people's interest in investing in sukuk (Hilman, 2022).

Research on the sharia sukuk capital market in sharia financial institutions experienced a slight increase from 2019 to 2021. Based on searches in Garuda page (Digital Reference Garba) scientific publication regarding the sharia sukuk capital market in sharia financial institutions from 2018 to 2022, there are 8 studies. In detail, in 2018 and 2019 there was only 1 study, while in 2020, 2021 and 2022 there were 2 studies. This shows that although research on the sharia sukuk capital market in sharia financial institutions has increased, the increase is not significant, indicating that the development of the sharia sukuk capital market in sharia financial institutions still requires a lot of space for research. Based on the matters stated above, the aim of the research is to determine the mapping of research around the Islamic capital market over a period of 19 years from 2004 to 2022 using the VOSViewer bibliometric method and literature review.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Islamic Capital Market is a capital market that operates in accordance with Islamic sharia principles, where the use of financial instruments that violate Islamic law such as *riba* (interest), *maysir* (speculation), and *gharar* (uncertainty or unpredictability) is avoided. The aim of the Islamic capital market is to provide investors with the opportunity to invest in financial instruments that comply with sharia principles. In the Islamic Capital Market, financial instruments that are generally traded include sukuk (sharia bonds), sharia shares, sharia mutual funds, and other financial instruments that meet sharia requirements. For example, sukuk is a financial instrument that is similar to conventional bonds, but does not contain elements of usury (Yuliana, 2019).

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature. Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well

as to understand interactions and relationships between scientific fields and publications (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept. VOSviewer can help researchers and analysts carry out citation network analysis, find relationships between scientific fields, and understand trends and issues in scientific literature (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Studies Literature review is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

III. METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is the Islamic Capital Market. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about the Islamic Capital Market originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Islamic Capital Market ", "Islamic Capital Market" and "Islamic Capital Market" for the entire year period (20 04 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature review studies (Budianto, 2022).

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding the Islamic Capital Market

The findings of this research were to examine the number of articles published on the Garuda website during the 2004-202 period 3. Based on data obtained from research

on the Garuda website, articles relating to the Islamic capital market, as many as 239 titles come from accredited national journals. In 2022, it was the year with the most publications, namely 52 publications. So, on average every year publications continue to increase by 15 publications.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding the Islamic Capital Market by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2004	1	2011	4	2015	18	2019	38
2006	1	2012	1	2016	15	2020	44
2008	1	2013	9	2017	25	2021	42
2009	4	2014	10	2018	27	2022	52
2010	1						
Total 239							

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2019.

4.2. Bibliometric Mapping of Research on the Islamic Capital Market

Article search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) data format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding the Islamic Capital Market

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer related to the research development map regarding the Islamic Capital Market in Sharia Financial Institutions, there are 13 clusters and 321 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1 (red) consists of 60 items, namely: Capital markets, Business, Contradict, Course, Fairly good, Capital Markets, DSN MUI, Islamic criteria, Islamic principle, Islamic regulation, Islamic sharia, istishna, long term, Islamic Capital Market concept, lie, muamalah, mudharabah, mudharabah contract, murabahah, musyarakah, thus, obligation, stock trading, perfect information, presence, price, sharia principles, product variation, investment products, prohibition, public accountant, usury, salam, science, sharia scara, securities company, shadaqah, sharia rule, sharia speculation, sharia, Islamic Capital Market, sharia obligation, short selling, sources, sharia securities, Islamic law, about capital markets, investment decisions, waqf and zakat.
- Cluster 2 (green) consists of 50 items, namely: abnormal return, announcement, bank, sharia bank, capital market reaction, case, classic assumption test, classical assumption test, contagion effect, conventional bank international, conventional bank, corporate sukuk, cumulative abnormal return, dividend policy, efficiency, equity, exchange rate, fair price, financial deepening, financial performance, firm value, inflation, initial return, interest rate, interest stock, irf, Islamic bank, Islamic financing, Islamic stock index, long term, market orientation, market power, market reaction, merger, movement, net profit margin, observation period, orientation, overreaction, partial effect, profitability, rating, regression model, significant impact, significant negative effect, study period, third party fund, test period, and vector error correction model.
- Cluster 3 (blue) consists of 43 items, namely: investing in the capital market, class, values, Islamic economics and business faculty, generation, Indonesian sharia stock index, intention, investment risk, Islam and staying away from things that are prohibited, Islamic banking study program, Islamic stock exchange, both variables, technological progress, information technology progress, then, knowledge variable, Islamic Capital Market, knowledge, investment knowledge, sellers and buyers, sharia banking, public interest, purposive sampling method, quantitative approach, mutual funds sharia, investment risk, significance value, significant difference, significant positive effect, significant to investment interest, significant to investment interest of Garut millennials, significance, stock account, sharia in transactions, count, table value, technological advance, technological progress, taking techniques sample, on investment interest, on investment interest, and to invest.
- Cluster 4 (mustard) consists of 36 items, namely: choice, deposit, dps, evaluation, financial capability, financial market, general public, halal returns fund, homework, Indonesian society, initial investment, investment activity, investment fund, investment management, investment manager, investment pattern, investment portfolio management, key words, legal protection, maximum absorption, modern investment instrument, mutual fund, necessary action, planning, portfolio management, sharia mutual funds, resale, selection, shareholder, sharia mutual fund, sharia mutual fund share,

sharia supervisory bid, special appeal, guerrilla strategy in encouraging Islamic Capital Market investment, supervision and sharia mutual funds.

- Cluster 5 (purple) consists of 25 items, namely: absolute authority, alternative dispute resolution, capital market transaction, conflict, dispute, effort, framework, guideline, Indonesia Islamic Capital Market, Islamic law regulation, legal vacuum, muamalah product, non litigation, rapid development, reference, religious court, religious court officials competency, Islamic Capital Market civil case, Islamic Capital Market dispute resolution, Islamic Capital Market law enforcement, Islamic Capital Market mediation, efforts, sharia points, stability and terms.
- Cluster 6 (light blue) consists of 22 items, namely: account, Islamic Capital Market sector, business screening, cooperation, financial, financial screening, investment gallery, implementation, capital market study group, kspm, legal opinion, limitation, majority, muslims, training through Islamic Capital Market schools, continuous opening of stock accounts, increasing the development of Islamic Capital Markets, Islamic Capital Market experts, Islamic Capital Market schools, human resources and Islamic Capital Markets.
- Cluster 7 (orange) consists of 21 items, namely: economics, results, from sharia mutual funds, related to research, content analysis, composite stock price index, Islamic Capital Market instruments are sharia shares, the strong role of the Islamic Capital Market, sharia capital, sharia bonds, long, Indonesian capital market, this research has benefits, the role of the Islamic Capital Market, the development of the Islamic Capital Market in driving the rate of economic growth, the development of the Islamic Capital Market, rating of sharia bond issuance, stakeholders, on economic growth, website and for industrial development.
- Cluster 8 (brown) consists of 19 items, namely: analysis of the performance of sharia stock mutual funds in the Indonesian capital market using the sharpe, benchmark, comparison, financial service authority, Indonesian capital market, Islamic stock fund performance data, market performance, measurement, operational definition methods, outperform performance, performance, period, positive performance, research sample, sharia mula fund, sharia pacific shares sharia stock fund, sharia stock mutual fund, sharpe method, sucorinvest sharia equity fund sharia mutual fund.
- Cluster 9 (pink) consists of 17 items, namely: in the capital market, phenomena, fundamental analysis, stock prices, implementation of Islamic Capital Market regulations in the sharia online trading system, Muslim investors in stock investment, Jakarta Islamic index period, npm, capital market and increasing sharia facilities, development of the Islamic Capital Market in Indonesia, companies, regulations, ROA, samples, which are significant for share prices, stock prices, trading systems.

- Cluster 10 (pink) consists of 9 items, namely: business capital, halal, illicit investment, negative perception, perception, public education, public knowledge, sharia business, trader.
- Cluster 11 (young hujau) consists of 8 items, namely: behavior, capital markets sharia Muslim woman, investment decision making, Lampung, Muslim investor, research show, social interaction, Islamic Capital Markets.
- Cluster 12 (sky blue) consists of 7 items, namely: conventional fixed income unit trust, investment performance, liquidity, net asset value, new net cash flow, quality, redemption moment.
- Cluster 13 (raw yellow) consists of 4 items, namely: capital market industry, Islamic capital market industry, legal certainly, legal system.

4.3. Mapping Literature Review regarding Problems in the Islamic Capital Market

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 12 problems in the Islamic Capital Market in general, namely:

First, criminal acts. In the Islamic Capital Market, criminal acts can be defined as actions that conflict with sharia principles in capital market transactions. Some examples of criminal acts in the Islamic capital market include insider trading, stock price manipulation, and fraud. When there is a criminal act in the Islamic Capital Market, the Islamic Capital Market authorities will provide sanctions in accordance with sharia principles, such as paying fines, refunding funds and social rehabilitation.

Second, the practice of Short Selling. Short selling is the practice of buying and selling shares in the capital market which is commonly carried out by conventional investors. However, the practice of short selling in the Islamic Capital Market is considered contrary to sharia principles because it involves speculation and usury. Therefore, the practice of short selling is not permitted in the Islamic capital market.

Third, comparison with the Conventional Capital Market. The Islamic Capital Market has different principles from the Conventional Capital Market, where the sharia principles applied in the Islamic Capital Market are to prohibit usury, gharar (uncertainty), and maisir (speculation). Investments in the Islamic Capital Market are made in companies operating in halal and ethical sectors, whereas in the Conventional Capital Market, investors can invest in companies in any sector without considering ethical principles.

Fourth, reputation risk management. Reputation risk management is very important for organizations operating in various sectors, including Islamic banking and finance, because a good reputation can increase trust and credibility among customers and investors. Reputation risk management can be done in several ways, such as: understanding customer needs and expectations, building good relationships with the media, monitoring and evaluating public sentiment towards the organization, and ensuring consistency between sharia values and the organization's business practices.

Fifth, the 4P marketing mix strategy in determining sharia business capital sources is a marketing concept consisting of four elements, namely: product, price, promotion and place. In the context of sharia business, the 4P marketing mix strategy can be used to determine sources of business capital by optimizing the advantages of sharia business. For the product element, sharia businesses can offer products that comply with sharia principles, such as halal investment or sharia financing. In the price element, sharia businesses can determine prices that are reasonable and in accordance with sharia values. In the promotion element, sharia businesses can promote products and services through media that are halal and do not conflict with sharia principles. In the place element, sharia businesses can place products and services in places that comply with sharia values, such as in shopping centers or family-friendly places.

Sixth, the difference between the Islamic Capital Market and the Sharia Money Market. Islamic Capital Market and Sharia Money Market are two types of financial markets that operate based on Islamic sharia principles. Although both operate under Islamic sharia principles, they have the following differences:

- (1) Types of Financial Instruments. The Islamic Capital Market focuses on long-term investment instruments such as shares, bonds and sukuk. Meanwhile, the Sharia Money Market focuses on short-term investment instruments such as deposits, commercial securities and mudharabah.
- (2) Role of Investors. Investors involved in the Islamic Capital Market are usually more oriented towards long-term portfolio development, while investors involved in the Sharia Money Market tend to prioritize short-term investment liquidity.
- (3) Risk, namely because instruments in the Islamic Capital Market are generally long-term investments, the risks associated with them are also greater. On the other hand, instruments in the Sharia Money Market tend to be safer because they are oriented towards short-term investments and have a lower level of risk.
- (4) The aim of investment is to develop long-term wealth, while the aim of investment in the Sharia Money Market is to secure and maintain the value of money in the short term.
- (5) Market Size. The Islamic Capital Market is generally larger and more complex than the Sharia Money Market, because it involves more and more varied long-term investment instruments. The Islamic Money Market, on the other hand, is smaller and simpler.
- (6) Sharia Compliance. Both financial markets are regulated by Islamic sharia principles, but the Islamic Capital Market has stricter sharia compliance standards because it involves more complex long-term investment instruments.

Seventh, screening system for sharia instruments and purification of non-halal income. The following are several steps in the sharia instrument screening system: (1) Identifying instruments traded on the Islamic Capital Market, such as

shares, bonds and mutual fund investment units; (2) Determine sharia criteria for each type of instrument, such as debt to equity ratio, percentage of income from sources prohibited according to sharia, and so on; (3) Analyze the financial statements of companies that issue instruments to check whether the company complies with established sharia criteria; (4) Assess other factors related to sharia principles, such as work environment, business ethics, and corporate social responsibility; and (5) Purifying non-halal income, namely eliminating income obtained from sources that are not in accordance with sharia principles, such as alcohol, tobacco, the gambling industry, and so on.

Eighth, comparison of conventional and sharia bond issuance. The issuance of conventional and sharia bonds has several main differences in the Islamic Capital Market: (1) Conventional bonds are issued based on the principle of usury or interest, while sharia bonds are issued based on the principle of profit sharing; (2) Conventional bonds use a loan agreement, while sharia bonds use a sale and purchase contract. purchase agreement) with the basic asset or underlying asset used as collateral; (3) Sharia bonds are supervised by the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) which is tasked with ensuring that bond issuance is carried out in accordance with sharia principles, while conventional bonds do not have special supervision; (4) Sharia bonds are attractive to investors who wish to invest in a manner that complies with sharia principles, while conventional bonds are attractive to investors who do not have sharia investment preferences; and (5) The level of profit offered on sharia bonds may be more varied compared to conventional bonds. This is because profits on sharia bonds depend on the profits generated by the underlying asset used as collateral, whereas profits on conventional bonds are determined at the time of issuance.

Ninth, the role of public accountants. Some of the main roles of public accountants in the Islamic capital market include: (1) Auditing financial reports; (2) Apart from conducting audits, public accountants can also assist companies in preparing financial reports in accordance with sharia principles and applicable accounting standards; (3) Public accountants can also provide counseling and consultation to companies regarding sharia principles and applicable accounting standards, as well as assist companies in fulfilling the requirements of Islamic Capital Market regulations; and (4) Public accountants are also responsible for ensuring that companies comply with sharia principles and applicable accounting standards in their financial reports, as well as ensuring that companies comply with Islamic Capital Market regulatory requirements.

Tenth, development of the JII-Analisa.com website as an optimum portfolio analysis tool using the covariance variance method, namely: (1) Providing information and services to Islamic capital market investors who wish to carry out portfolio analysis and select optimal investments based on the covariance variance method; (2) Create a website display design that is attractive, user-friendly, and easy for users to understand; (3) Collecting Islamic Capital Market data required for portfolio analysis, such as share price data, company financial data, and other

relevant data; (4) Creating an optimal portfolio analysis model using the variance covariance method, which can assist investors in choosing an investment portfolio that suits their risk profile and investment objectives; (5) Applying sophisticated data processing and data analysis technology to process Islamic capital market data and produce accurate and fast portfolio analysis; (6) Providing interactive features on the JII-Analisa.com website, such as risk calculators, stock performance charts, and investment recommendations, so that users can easily understand the results of portfolio analysis and choose investments that suit their needs; (7) Testing the JII-Analisa.com website and correcting errors found, as well as updating existing features so that they can respond to developing user needs; (8) Promoting and marketing the JII-Analisa.com website to target users, such as Islamic Capital Market investors, sharia financial institutions, and Islamic Capital Market related institutions; and (9) Establishing cooperation with related parties, such as sharia financial institutions, Islamic Capital Market associations, and educational institutions that provide study programs related to Islamic Capital Markets.

Eleventh, the regulation and supervisory role of the OJK regarding the screening of Islamic Capital Market shares. The following are several things carried out by the OJK in regulating and supervising share screening in the Islamic Capital Market: (1) the OJK determines the criteria for sharia shares that must be met by companies wishing to be listed on the sharia stock exchange, including aspects such as source of income, debt ratio on equity, and business activities that are permitted according to sharia principles; (2) OJK also supervises the assessment of sharia stock indices which are used as a reference for investors in selecting sharia shares, where sharia stock indexes usually include shares of companies that meet the sharia criteria set by the OJK; (3) OJK also regulates the activities of securities companies operating in the Islamic Capital Market, including in terms of stock screening, where securities companies must ensure that the shares they offer to investors meet the sharia criteria set by the OJK; (4) OJK also monitors violations of established sharia criteria and takes action if violations occur, such as imposing sanctions or revoking business permits.

Twelfth, principle. Several principles implemented in the Islamic Capital Market include: (1) Mudharabah Principle, namely investors who provide capital and managers who manage that capital. The profits generated are then shared according to the agreement; (2) Musyarakah principle, which involves two or more parties pooling capital to start a business, where profits and losses are shared according to the agreement; (3) Murabahah principle, which involves the sale of goods at a price that is openly disclosed, where the price includes production costs, capital costs and expected profits; (4) Wakalah principle, which involves a third party acting as a representative or intermediary in carrying out transactions, where this third party acts on behalf of the investor and is responsible for selecting investment instruments that comply with sharia principles; and (5) Ijarah principle, which involves renting or using goods or services with pre-agreed rental or wage payments, which is a principle often used in investments in the property or real estate sector.

Thirteenth, work system. The working system in the Islamic Capital Market prioritizes transparency, fairness and compliance with sharia principles. The Islamic Capital Market working system involves several entities, namely: (1) Sharia Supervisory Institution, namely the institution tasked with assessing whether the investment products or instruments offered comply with sharia principles; (2) Guarantee Institution, namely the institution responsible for providing guarantees against losses that may occur as a result of investments made; (3) Securities Companies, namely companies responsible for carrying out sharia securities buying and selling transactions, as well as providing information and services for investors; and (4) Investors, namely parties who provide capital to invest in the Islamic Capital Market.

4.4. Mapping Literature Review regarding Juridical Aspects of the Islamic Capital Market

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 12 juridical aspects of the Islamic Capital Market, namely:

First, Legal Opinion of the Capital Market Sharia Expert/ASPM. This legal opinion is used by companies, investors and financial institutions to ensure that the investment products they offer comply with sharia principles. ASPM usually provides legal opinions on investment products which include instruments such as sharia bonds, sharia shares, sharia mutual funds, and other products that comply with sharia principles. This legal opinion includes a legal analysis of the structure of the investment product, and ensures that the product does not conflict with sharia principles, such as the prohibition of usury, gharar (uncertainty), maysir (gambling), and other haram.

Second, transaction instruments and mechanisms, namely: (1) Shares registered on the stock exchange that meet sharia criteria, namely not being involved in prohibited businesses such as alcohol, tobacco, gambling and usury; (2) Bonds issued in accordance with sharia principles, such as not containing fixed interest and not containing elements of speculation; (3) Mutual funds that invest in sharia shares and bonds, and fulfill sharia criteria in managing their portfolios; (4) In the Islamic Capital Market, transactions are carried out electronically using an online trading system; (5) Settlement of transactions in the Islamic Capital Market is carried out using an accounting system that complies with sharia principles, such as contracts and guarantees; (6) Sharia derivative instruments are instruments used to hedge market or speculative risks in the Islamic Capital Market, which must meet sharia criteria in terms of their use and must be supervised by the appropriate regulatory body; and (7) Sharia guarantee is a guarantee provided by an institution or company to protect investors from losses caused by failure to carry out transactions, which must comply with sharia principles and be supervised by the appropriate regulatory body.

Third, Fatwa of the Indonesian Ulema Council No. 40/DSN-MUI/X/2003, has a significant influence in the Islamic Capital Market in Indonesia. This fatwa was

issued as a guide for Muslims who wish to invest in the capital market according to sharia principles. Several important points from this fatwa include: (1) Investments in the capital market must be in accordance with sharia principles, such as the principles of justice, halal and openness; (2) In stock investments, investors are not allowed to buy shares in companies operating in sectors prohibited by sharia, such as companies operating in the fields of alcohol, gambling or pornography; (3) Investors must evaluate the company's performance and check whether the company meets sharia financial requirements, such as not having high debt or not committing usury in financial management; and (4) Investors must pay attention to how the company manages profits and ensure that the profits received come from halal business activities.

Fourth, legislation. Legislation in the Islamic capital market is based on the principles of sharia or Islamic law, which makes it possible to carry out investment activities in a manner that is in accordance with Islamic values. The following are several laws and regulations related to the Islamic capital market:

- (1) Law Number 8 of 1995 concerning Capital Markets, which provides a framework for capital markets in Indonesia. This law was then amended and perfected with the issuance of Law Number 19 of 2016 concerning Amendments to Law Number 8 of 1995 concerning Capital Markets.
- (2) Financial Services Authority (OJK) Regulation Number 77/POJK.04/2016 concerning the Application of Sharia Principles to Financial Sector Business Activities, which provides guidelines for implementing financial sector business activities in accordance with sharia principles.
- (3) OJK Regulation Number 1/POJK.05/2013 concerning the Issuance and Offering of Sharia Securities, which regulates the requirements for the issuance and offering of sharia securities, including the assessment of sharia securities, use of proceeds from the offering, and reporting.
- (4) National Sharia Council (DSN) Fatwa on Islamic Capital Markets, which is a fatwa issued by DSN as the highest sharia authority in Indonesia, which regulates sharia principles that must be followed in the Islamic Capital Market.
- (5) Other regulations related to the Islamic Capital Market, such as the Regulation of the Minister of Finance concerning the Implementation of Sharia-Based Pension Fund Investments and the Regulation of the Minister of Religion concerning Certification of Sharia Financial Products.

Fifth, legal protection for investors. Several forms of legal protection provided include the following: (1) The Islamic Capital Market Law provides the legal basis for the implementation of the Islamic Capital Market and provides protection to investors. This law stipulates obligations for issuers and parties involved in the Islamic Capital Market to fulfill established standards and requirements, as well as provide accurate, transparent and clear information to investors. (2) Financial Services Authority (OJK) regulations. OJK issues various regulations and policies to protect investors' interests, including regulations regarding requirements for issuing

and trading sharia investment instruments, provisions for Islamic Capital Market transactions, as well as provisions regarding supervision and reporting. (3) Clearing and Guarantee Institution. This institution provides guarantees for the financial obligations of the parties involved in the transaction, so that investors will feel safer when investing in the Islamic capital market. (4) Civil and Criminal Laws also provide protection for investors in the Islamic capital market. If there is an act of fraud, market manipulation, or other violations that harm investors, investors can file a lawsuit and file a civil or criminal lawsuit against the party responsible.

Sixth, legal reconstruction of dispute resolution using Online Dispute Resolution/ODR. The following are several things that need to be considered: (1) ODR can help increase openness and transparency in resolving disputes in the Islamic capital market; (2) ODR must also ensure the security and privacy of personal data and trade secrets related to disputes in the Islamic capital market; (3) The use of ODR in resolving disputes in the Islamic Capital Market must pay attention to sharia principles; (4) ODR must be used within a clear and well-defined legal framework; (5) ODR must be designed to provide sustainable dispute resolution solutions.

Seventh, Sharia Supervisory Board Regulations. The following are several things you need to know regarding DPS regulations in the Islamic Capital Market: (1) DPS has the function of an independent supervisor and advisor in maintaining compliance with sharia principles in the Islamic Capital Market; (2) DPS has an important role in the decision-making process in the Islamic Capital Market; (3) DPS regulations on the Islamic Capital Market are regulated in Law Number 8 of 1995 concerning Capital Markets and its implementing regulations; (4) DPS consists of a number of ulama and sharia finance experts who have qualifications and experience in the fields of sharia law and sharia finance; (5) DPS has the obligation to supervise public companies that issue sharia securities and sharia financial products traded on the Islamic Capital Market; and (6) If there is a violation of sharia principles in the Islamic Capital Market, the DPS has the authority to impose appropriate sanctions.

Eighth, Islamic legal perspective. The perspective of Islamic law on the Islamic capital market is very positive. The Islamic Capital Market is based on Islamic sharia principles which emphasize justice, transparency and togetherness in investing. Islamic sharia principles used in the Islamic Capital Market include the prohibition of usury, gharar and maysir.

Ninth, Fukaha's thoughts. Some of his important thoughts are: (1) According to Fukaha, transactions in the Islamic capital market must be clear and transparent so as not to cause uncertainty or doubt among the parties involved; (2) Fukaha views that investment in the Islamic Capital Market must be in accordance with sharia principles, such as the prohibition of usury, speculation and gambling; (3) Fukaha considers profit sharing or distribution of profits between investors and companies as a fair form of cooperation; and (4) Fukaha views that investment in the Islamic Capital Market must have a positive impact on society and the surrounding environment.

Tenth, theoretical philosophical review. In a theoretical philosophical review, the Islamic capital market views that money and wealth are gifts from Allah SWT which must be managed well to achieve beneficial goals. The sharia principles that form the basis of the Islamic Capital Market include the prohibition of usury (riba al-fadl and riba al-nasi'ah), gharar (uncertainty), maysir (gambling), and the prohibition of unclear and unfair transactions. This aims to maintain fairness in financial transactions and avoid all forms of loss and injustice.

Eleventh, practical philosophical review. From a practical philosophical perspective, the Islamic capital market has the same principles as the conventional capital market in terms of investment management, namely seeking maximum profits with as little risk as possible. However, the Islamic capital market views that investment must be carried out responsibly by respecting sharia values and paying attention to the welfare of society. Therefore, investment in the Islamic capital market must be made in companies that have good financial performance, uphold sharia principles, and have clear benefits for society.

Twelfth, review of Maqashid Syariah. In Maqashid Syariah's review of the Islamic capital market, it should be noted that the Islamic capital market is not only about meeting the technical requirements of Sharia, but also about achieving broader Islamic goals. Therefore, there needs to be continuous efforts to ensure that the Islamic Capital Market continues to innovate and adapt to existing challenges, so that it can continue to achieve the goals of Maqashid Syariah.

4.6. Mapping Literature Review regarding Determinant Variables of Public Interest and Satisfaction in Investing in the Islamic Capital Market

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 46 variables determining people's interest and satisfaction in investing in the Islamic Capital Market, namely: (1) Knowledge; (2) Financial literacy; (3) Training; (4) Investment gallery; (5) Fun Boss Game; (6) Intelligence; (7) Education; (8) Social motives; (9) Information media; (10) Economic motive; (11) Encouragement from within oneself; (12) Emotional; (13) Portfolio return; (14) Sharia attributes; (15) Gender; (16) Seminars; (17) Education; (18) Risk level; (19) Information Asymmetry; (20) Ethical investment; (21) Experience; (22) Length of investment; (23) Employment; (24) Income; (25) Religion/Religiosity; (26) Investment plan; (27) Confidence; (28) Halal profit sharing; (29) Positive impression; (30) Portfolio diversification; (31) Yield performance; (32) Investment trends; (33) Participation in sharia financial development; (34) Technological progress; (35) Benefits; (36) Investment considerations; (37) Understanding; (38) Efficiency; (39) Cyber Public Relations - based communication strategy; (40) Guerrilla strategies raise public awareness; (41) Study group; (42) Minimum capital; (43) Income; (44) Motivation; (45) Technical Analysis; and (46) Sharia compliance.

4.7. Mapping Literature Review regarding the Effects and Determining Variables of Islamic Capital Market Performance

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 10 influences caused by the Islamic Capital Market, namely: (1) Sustainable legal development/Sustainable and Responsible Investment; (2) Economic growth; (3) Source of financing; (4) Oil prices; (5) Fed Rate; (6) Interest Rate; (7) Dow Jones Index; (8) Currency exchange rates; (9) Inflation; and (10) Financial Deepening

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 23 variables determining the performance of the Islamic Capital Market, namely: (1) Covid-19 pandemic; (2) Lifestyle of female investors; (3) Indonesian Sharia Stock Price Index; (4) 2008 global financial crisis; (5) Trading Sharia Composite Stock Index; (6) Macroeconomic variables, including: inflation, currency exchange rates; (7) Conventional Bank Interest; (8) Sharia Bank Merger; (9) Company fundamental variables, including: Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR, Current Ratio/CR, Net Profit Margin/NPM, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Earning Per Share/EPS; (10) Sukuk, including: issuance value, rating, risk; (11) Global economic performance; (12) Islamic Defense Action 212; (13) Application of sharia principles; (14) Announcement of a trade balance deficit; (15) Political events in the event of Donald Trump's victory; (16) Stock Splits; (17) BPKH Investment; (18) Announcement of financial reports; (19) Systematic risk; (20) Islamic economic principles; (21) Sharia securities offering; and (23) Halal industry.

4.8. Mapping Literature Review regarding Islamic Capital Market Products

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 9 types of Islamic Capital Market products, namely: (1) Derivative Products; (2) Sharia Mutual Funds; (3) Sukuk; (4) Sharia Online Trading System/SOTS; (5) Sadaqah shares; (6) Zakat on shares; (7) Share waqf; (8) Ijarah, Istishna, Kafalah, Mudharabah, Musyarakah, Wakalah contracts; and (9) Integration of waqf and sukuk.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding the Islamic Capital Market during the period 2004 to 2022, with a total number of publications is 239 research articles.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding the Islamic Capital Market are divided into 13 clusters and 321 items. Cluster 1 consists of 60 items, cluster 2 consists of 50 items, cluster 3 consists of 43 items, cluster 4 consists of 36 items, cluster 5 consists of 25 items, cluster 6 consists of 22 items, cluster 7 consists of 21 items, cluster 8 consists of 19 items, cluster 9 consists of 17 items, cluster 10 consists of 9 items, cluster 11 consists of 8 items, cluster 12 consists of 7 items, and cluster 13 consists of 4 items.
- Based on the literature review, there are 6 main themes of research regarding the Islamic Capital Market, namely: (1) Problems in the Islamic Capital Market; (2) Juridical aspects; (3) Determinant variables of people's interest

and satisfaction in investing; (4) The impact caused; (5) Performance determinant variables; and (6) Islamic Capital Market Products.

is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- The results of the e- review literature study can be explained in a more complex way.

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